

Fixed point theorem between cone metric space and quasi-cone metric space

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ABSTRACT

This study involves new notions of continuity of mapping between quasi-cone metrics spaces (QCMSs), cone metric spaces (CMSs), and vice versa. The relation between all notions of continuity were thoroughly studied and supported with the help of examples. In addition, these new continuities were compared with various types of continuities of mapping between two QCMSs. The continuity types are **ff**-continuous, **bb**-continuous, **fb**-continuous, and **bf**-continuous. The results demonstrated that the new notions of continuity could be generalized to the continuity of mapping between two QCMSs. It also showed a fixed point for this continuity map between a complete Hausdorff CMS and QCMS. Overall, this study supports recent research results.

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1. INTRODUCTION

More than two decades ago, Huang and Zhang had proposed the notion of a cone metric space [1]. The Cauchy and convergent sequences and a few fixed-point theorems were used for the contractive form of mappings in cone metric spaces (CMSs). This notion is exciting because of the usual metric space where an ordered Banach space switches to the real numbers. Abbas and Jungck [2] have shown some noncommuting mapping causes CMSs. Furthermore, several researchers have proved different contractive-type maps in CMS and fixed points [3]-[8].

The function of a quasi-metric is to verify the triangle disparity. However, quasi-metric is considered an asymmetric metric. As compared to metric space, quasi-metric space (QMS) is more inclusive. It is also a topic of exhaustive research in computer science and the framework for topology. For instance, a quasi-cone metric space (QCMS) definition expands to the QMS given by Turkoglu and Abuloha [3]. Morales and Rojas have introduced the continuity of mapping between CMS (X, C) , P a cone along with constant K and $T: X \rightarrow X$ and it self [4]. Yaying *et al.* introduced the continuity of mapping between QCMS (X, q) and itself [5]. In addition, although the concept of normality in CMSs is monumental in developing fixed point theory in CMSs, Rezapour and Hambarani [6] have rejected it. Several researchers have simplified fixed points in CMSs in many directions. For instance, Jankovic *et al.* [7] surveyed the latest outcomes in CMSs. Abdeljawad and Karapinar [8] have verified fixed point theorems in QCMSs. They introduced many Cauchy sequences in QCMSs, which are studied as an extension of the Banach contraction

mapping and other areas. Yaying *et al.* [9] have defined arithmetic *fb*- continuity and arithmetic *ff*-continuity based on the notions of forward and backward arithmetic convergence in asymmetric metric spaces. Also, they have proven some interesting results.

For functions between (MSs), (CMSs) and (QCMSs) and themselves, many continuity ideas have been established [4], [5]. The continuity function between (QCMSs) and (CMSs) and vice versa, however, has yet to be implemented. As a result, we have introduced these definitions and looked at how they relate to one another. Our ideas are based on the continuation of a function mapping between two (MSs), a function mapping between two (CMSs), and a function mapping between two (QCMSs). There have been numerous fixed-point theorems presented between (MSs) and themselves, (CMSs) and themselves, and (QCMSs) and themselves [1], [8]. We looked at prior results of a fixed-point to introduce a fixed point in a function mapping between (CMSs) and (QCMSs).

This paper introduces new notions of continuity of mapping, some theorems, and propositions. It compares the new notions to each other through specific examples. Additionally, the paper introduces the fixed-point theorem of the newly introduced notion. The paper also supports the results of other recent research with the help of examples. Finally, some general concepts, definitions, and outcomes are recalled and applied in this paper.

This study will make a significant contribution to the field of mapping continuity and fixed-point theorems. Fixed point theorems are used to solve problems in estimate theory, game theory, and mathematical economics in a variety of disciplines including mathematics, statistics, computer science, engineering, and economics. The following is how the rest of the paper is structured: The study's preliminary findings are presented in section 2, the results are clarified in section 3, and the paper is completed in section 4.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this part, the elementary facts about the CMSs and QCMSs and their continuity, which can be observed in [1], [10]-[26], are given in a shortened form.

- Definition 2. 1 (see [17]). The cone is considered to be regular if each expanding sequence in P that is bounded from is convergent in E . If $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence such that,

$$u_1 \leq u_2 \leq \dots \leq u_n \leq \dots \leq v \tag{1}$$

for a few $v \in E$, there is also some $u \in E$ that satisfies $\|u_n - u\| \rightarrow 0_E$. As $(n \rightarrow \infty)$.

In the following, we continually assume E is a space of Banach, P is a cone.

- Definition 2. 2 (see [18]). Assume X is a nonempty set. Presume the mapping $C : X \times X \rightarrow E$ assures,
 - (C1) $C(u, v) \geq 0_E$ for all $u, v \in X$ and $C(u, v) = 0_E$ if and only if $u = v$
 - (C2) $C(u, v) = C(v, u)$ for all $u, v \in X$
 - (C3) $C(u, v) \leq C(u, w) + C(v, w)$ for all $u, v, w \in X$
 then, C is a cone metric on X , and (X, C) is a CMS.
- Proposition 2. 3 (see [4]). Assume (X, C_1) and (Y, C_2) are a CMS, P a cone with constant K and $T: X \rightarrow Y$. The following are equivalent,
 - the map T is continuous.
 - If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n = u$, implies that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tu_n = Tu$ for every $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X .
- Definition 2. 4 (see [24]). Assume X is a set. Presume that the mapping $q: X \times X \rightarrow E$ satisfies the subsequent,
 - (Q1) $0_E \leq q(u, v)$ for all $u, v \in X$,
 - (Q2) $q(u, v) = 0_E$ if and only if $u = v$,
 - (Q3) $q(u, v) \leq q(u, w) + q(w, v)$, for all $u, v, w \in X$.
 Then, q is known as a QCM on X , and the pair (X, q) is called a QCMS.
- Example 2. 5 (see [25]). Assume $X = \mathbb{R}$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $P = \{(u, v) \in E : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (2),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (0,0) & \text{if } u = v, \\ (1,0) & \text{if } u > v, \\ (0,1) & \text{if } u < v. \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Then, $(q, \mathbb{R})$ is a QCMS because it satisfies all conditions of QCMS, for all $u, v, w \in \mathbb{R}$.

- Definition 2. 6 (see [27]). A sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ forward converges to $u_0 \in X$ if for each $c \in E$ along with $0_E \ll c$ (i.e., $c \in \text{int } P$) there exists a number n_0 that satisfies $q(u_0, u_n) \ll c$ for all $n \geq n_0$. We indicate it through $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u_0$.
- Definition 2. 7 (see [3]). A sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ backward joins to $u_0 \in X$ if for each $c \in E$ along with $0_E \ll c$ (i.e., $c \in \text{int } P$) there is a number n_0 that satisfies $q(u_n, u_0) \ll c$ for all $n \geq n_0$. We show it by $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u_0$.
- Definition 2. 8 (see [5]). Assume (X, q_X) and (Y, q_Y) are two QCMSs. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is *ff*-continuous at $u \in X$ if whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ in (X, q_X) we have $T(u_n) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ in (Y, q_Y) .
- Definition 2. 9 (see [5]). Assume (X, q_X) and (Y, q_Y) are two QCMSs. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is *fb*-continuous at $u \in X$ if whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ in (X, q_X) we have $T(u_n) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ in (Y, q_Y) .
- Definition 2. 10 (see [5]). Assume (X, q_X) and (Y, q_Y) are two QCMSs. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is *bf*-continuous at $u \in X$ if whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$ in (X, q_X) we have $T(u_n) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ in (Y, q_Y) .
- Definition 2. 11 (see [5]). Assume (X, q_X) and (Y, q_Y) are two QCMSs. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is *bb*-continuous at $u \in X$ if whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{b} x$ in (X, q_X) we have $T(u_n) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ in (Y, q_Y) .
- Definition 2. 12 (see [5]). A set X is compact in the forward sequence if every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X possesses a forward convergent subsequence $\{u_{n_k}\}_{n_k \in \mathbb{N}}$ to $u_0 \in X$ if for all $c \in E$ along with $0_E \ll c$ (i.e., $c \in \text{int } P$) there is number n_0 as a result $q(u_0, u_{n_k}) \ll c$ for all $n_k \geq n_0$.
- Definition 2. 13 (see [5]). A set X is compact in the backward sequence if every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X possesses a backward convergent subsequence $\{u_{n_k}\}_{n_k \in \mathbb{N}}$ to $u_0 \in X$ if for all $c \in E$ along with $0_E \ll c$ (i.e., $c \in \text{int } P$) there exists a number n_0 as a result $q(u_{n_k}, u_0) \ll c$ for all $n_k \geq n_0$.
- Lemma 2. 14 (see [5]). Assume (X, q) is a QCMS. Then $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$ if and only if each subsequence of it is backward convergent to u .
 Proof. Suppose $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$. Then for $c \in E$ along with $0_E \ll c$ there exists an $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $q(u_n, u) \ll c$, which means $c - q(u_n, u) \in \text{int } P$ for all $n \geq n_0$. Suppose $\{u_{n_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a random subsequence of $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. If $n_k \geq n_0$, we got $c - q(u_{n_k}, u) \in \text{int } P$, i.e., $q(u_{n_k}, u) \ll c$. So $u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{b} u$.
- Lemma 2. 15 (see [5]). Assume (X, q) is a QCMS. Then $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ if and only if each subsequence of it is forward convergent to u .
 Proof. Suppose $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$. Then, for $c \in E$ along sequence with $0_E \ll c$ there exists an $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ that satisfies $q(u, u_n) \ll c$, which means $c - q(u, u_n) \in \text{int } P$ for all $n \geq n_0$. Suppose $\{u_{n_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a random subsequence of $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. If $n_k \geq n_0$, we got $c - q(u, u_{n_k}) \in \text{int } P$, i.e., $q(u, u_{n_k}) \ll c$. So $u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{f} u$.
 The converse' proof is evident. Thus, it is removed. As a result, the proof is complete.
- Lemma 2. 16 (see [5]). If $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ forward converges to $u \in X$ and backward converges to $v \in X$, it means $u = v$.
- Theorem 2. 17 (see [5]). Assume $q : X \times X \rightarrow E$ is a QCMS. If (X, q) is a forward sequentially compact and $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$. It means $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$.

3. MAIN RESULTS

Because of the established concepts in CMSs and QCMSs [5] and [26], we introduce new notions of continuity of mapping between QCMS and CMS and vice versa. The relation between all notions of continuity is thoroughly studied and support with the help of examples. We also find a fixed point for this continuity map between a complete Hausdorff CMS and QCMS.

- Definition 3.1. Suppose (X, q) is a QCMS and (Y, C) a CMS. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is *b*-continuous at u if for any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X backward converges to an element u in X ($u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$), then the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to $T(u)$ in Y , $(C(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$). T is considered *b*-continuous if it is *b*-continuous at each $u \in X$.
- Example 3.2. Suppose (X, q) is a QCMS where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (3),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (u - v, \alpha(u - v)), & \text{if } u \geq v, \\ (\alpha, 1), & \text{if } u < v. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

assume (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0,1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. A map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{2}$ is b -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Proposition 3.3. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is b -continuous at u . Then, a map T is bb -continuous at u and bf -continuous at u .

Proof. Since a map $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is b -continuous at u , then for every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (X, q) that backward converges to an element u in (X, q) , i.e., $q(u_n, u) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that converges to $T(u)$ in (Y, C) , i.e., $C(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where every CMS is QCMS and $C(T(u_n), T(u)) = C(T(u), T(u_n)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, thus, a map T is bb -continuous at u and bf -continuous at u .

- Remark 3.4. Every bb -continuous (or bf -continuous) is not always the case b -continuous as every QCMS is not always CMS.
- Definition 3.5. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS and (Y, C) a CMS. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is f -continuous at u if for any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X forward converges to an element u in (X, q) ($u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$). Then, the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ approaches to $T(u)$ in (Y, C) ($C(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$). T is considered f -continuous if it is f -continuous at all $u \in X$.
- Example 3.6. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS, where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0,1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (4),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (v - u, \alpha(v - u)), & \text{if } v \geq u, \\ (\alpha, 1), & \text{if } v < u. \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

suppose (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0,1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. A map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{3}$ is f -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Proposition 3.7. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is f -continuous at x . Then, a map T is ff -continuous at x and fb -continuous at x . Proof. Since a map $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is f -continuous at u , then for all sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (X, q) forward approaches to an element u in (X, q) , i.e., $q(u, u_n) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that converges to $T(u)$ in (Y, C) , i.e., $C(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where every CMS is QCMS and $C(T(u_n), T(u)) = C(T(u), T(u_n)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, thus, a map T is ff -continuous at u and fb -continuous at u .

- Remark 3.8. Every ff -continuous (or fb -continuous) is not always the case f -continuous as every QCMS is not CMS.

- Theorem 3.9. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is b -continuous at u . If (X, q) is forward sequentially compact, then, T is f -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is b -continuous at u , any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X backward converges to $u \in X$. Then, the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ approaches to $T(u) \in Y$.

In other words, $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u \implies T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where (X, q) is forward sequentially compact, the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ possesses a forward convergent subsequence in X say $u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{f} v$ by Lemma 2.15, so $u_n \xrightarrow{f} v \in X$. Since $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u \in X$ and $u_n \xrightarrow{f} v \in X$ by Lemma 2.16, subsequently $u = v$. Thus, $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$. Since $T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, so $T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then, T is f -continuous at u .

- Example 3.10. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0,1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in E: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (5),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (0,0) & \text{if } v \geq u, \\ (u, \alpha u) & \text{if } v < u. \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

Assume (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0,1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in E: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. A map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{4}$ is b -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Lemma 3.11. Assume $q: X \times X \rightarrow E$ is a QCM. If (X, q) is backward sequentially compact and $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$. Then $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$.

Proof. Assume $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence so $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ for a few $u \in X$. Via the backward sequentially compactness, the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a backward convergent subsequence, as $u_{n_k} \xrightarrow{b} v$ by lemma 2.14, so, $u_n \xrightarrow{b} v$. Since $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u \in X$ and $u_n \xrightarrow{b} v \in X$, by Lemma 2.16, subsequently $u = v$. Thus, $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$.

- Theorem 3.12. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is f -continuous at x . If (X, q) is backward sequentially compact. Then, T is b -continuous at x .

Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is f -continuous at u that means any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X forward converges to $u \in X$. Then, a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ approaches to $T(u) \in Y$. In other words, $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u \implies T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, by Lemma 3.11, so $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$. Since $T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{f} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, so $T(u_n) \rightarrow T(u)$ whenever $u_n \xrightarrow{b} u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then, T is b -continuous at u .

- Example 3.13. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS where $X = [0, 1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in E : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (6),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (0, 0) & \text{if } u \geq v, \\ (v, \alpha v) & \text{if } u < v. \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

assume (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0, 1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in E : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. A map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{3}$ is f -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Remarks 3.14. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS and $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ a backward convergent sequence in X , the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is not always the case a forward convergent sequence in X . Assume (X, q) is a QCMS and $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ a forward convergent sequence in X , the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is not always the case a backward convergent sequence in X .

- Corollary 3.15. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is b -continuous at x . If (X, q) is forward sequentially compact, then T is bb -continuous, bf -continuous, fb -continuous and ff -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is b -continuous at u and (X, q) is forward sequentially compact by – Proposition 3.3, a map T is bb -continuous and bf -continuous at u , and by Theorem 3.9, a map T is f -continuous then, by Proposition 3.7, a map T is ff -continuous and fb -continuous at u .

- Corollary 3.16. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, C)$ is f -continuous at u . If (X, q) is backward sequentially compact, then T is bb -continuous, bf -continuous, fb -continuous and ff -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is b -continuous at u and (X, q) is backward sequentially compact by Proposition 3.7, a map T is ff -continuous and fb -continuous at u , and by Theorem 3.12, a map T is b -continuous then, by Proposition 3.3, a map T is bb -continuous and bf -continuous at u .

- Definition 3.17. Assume (X, C) is a CMS and (Y, q) a QCMS. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is b^* -continuous at u if for any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (X, C) converges to an element u in (X, C) , $(C(u_n, x) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$).

Then, a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (Y, q) backward converges to $T(u)$ in (Y, q) ($T(u_n) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$). Provided T is b^* -continuous at each $u \in X$, then it is called b^* -continuous.

- Example 3.18. Assume (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0, 1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. Suppose (X, q) is a QCMS where $X = [0, 1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (7),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (u - v, \alpha(u - v)), & \text{if } u \geq v, \\ (\alpha, 1), & \text{if } u < v. \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

a map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{2}$ is b^* -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Definition 3.19. Assume (X, C) is a CMS and (Y, q) a QCMS. A map $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is f^* -continuous at u if for any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (X, C) converges to an element u in (X, C) ($C(u_n, u) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$).

Then, a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (Y, q) forward converges to $T(u)$ in (Y, q) ($T(u_n) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$). Provided T is f^* -continuous at each $u \in X$, then it is called f^* -continuous.

- Example 3.20. Assume (X, C) is a CMS where $X = [0, 1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $P = \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : u, v \geq 0\}$ and $C: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by $C(u, v) = (|u - v|, \alpha|u - v|)$. Assume (X, q) is a QCMS

where $X = [0,1]$, $E = \mathbb{R}^2$, $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, $= \{(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2: u, v \geq 0\}$ and $q: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ is defined by (8),

$$q(u, v) = \begin{cases} (v - u, \alpha(v - u)), & \text{if } v \geq u, \\ (\alpha, 1), & \text{if } v < u. \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

a map $T: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ defined by $T(u) = \frac{u}{3}$ is f^* -continuous at $\{0\}$.

- Proposition 3.21. Assume $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is b^* -continuous at u . Then, a map T is bb -continuous at u and fb -continuous at u .

Proof. Since a map $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is b^* -continuous at u , then for every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (Y, C) approaches to an element u in (Y, C) , i.e., $C(u_n, u) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that backward approaches to $T(u)$ in (X, q) , i.e., $q(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where every CMS is QCMS and $C(u_n, u) = C(u, u_n) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, a map T is bb -continuous at u and fb -continuous at u .

- Remark 3.22. Assume $T: (X, q) \rightarrow (Y, q)$ is bb -continuous at u , or fb -continuous at u ; then, a map T is not b^* -continuous at u because not every QCMS is necessarily CMS.

- Proposition 3.23. Assume $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is f^* -continuous at u . Then a map T is ff -continuous at u and bf -continuous at u .

Proof. Since a map $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is f^* -continuous at u , then for any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in (Y, C) approaches to an element u in (Y, C) , i.e., $C(u_n, u) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have a sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that forward approaches to $T(u)$ in (X, q) , i.e., $q(T(u_n), T(u)) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where every CMS is a QCMS and $C(u_n, u) = C(u, u_n) \rightarrow 0_E$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, a map T is ff -continuous at u and bf -continuous at u .

- Theorem 3.24. Assume $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is b^* -continuous at u . If (X, q) is forward sequentially compact, then T is f^* -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: Y \rightarrow X$ is b^* -continuous at u , every sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Y converges to $u \in Y$, then the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ backward approaches to $T(u) \in X$. In other words, $u_n \rightarrow u \implies T(u_n) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where (X, q) is forward sequentially compact, the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a forward convergent subsequence in X say $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(v)$ by Lemma 2.15, so $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(v) \in X$. Since $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(u) \in X$ and $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(v) \in X$ by Lemma 2.16, subsequently $T(u) = T(v)$. Thus, $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$. Since $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ whenever $u_{n_k} \rightarrow u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ whenever $u_{n_k} \rightarrow u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then, T is f^* -continuous at u .

- Theorem 3.25. Assume $T: (Y, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is f^* -continuous at u . If (X, q) is backward sequentially compact, then T is b^* -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: Y \rightarrow X$ is f^* -continuous at u , then any sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in Y converges to $u \in Y$, then the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ forward approaches to $T(u) \in X$.

In other words, $u_n \rightarrow u \implies T(u_n) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, where (X, q) is backward sequentially compact, the sequence $\{T(u_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a backward convergent subsequence in X say $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(v)$ by Lemma 2.14, so $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(v) \in X$. Since $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(u) \in X$ and $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(v) \in X$ by Lemma 2.16, subsequently $T(u) = T(v)$. Thus, $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$. Since $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{f} T(u)$ whenever $u_{n_k} \rightarrow u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, so $T(u_{n_k}) \xrightarrow{b} T(u)$ whenever $u_{n_k} \rightarrow u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then T is b^* -continuous at u . Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is f^* -continuous at u and (X, q) is backward sequentially compact by Proposition 3.23, a map T is f -continuous and bf -continuous at u , and by Theorem 3.25, a map T is b^* -continuous then, by Proposition 3.21, a map T is bb -continuous and fb -continuous at u .

- Corollary 3.26. Assume $T: (X, C) \rightarrow (Y, q)$ is b^* -continuous at u , if (Y, q) is forward sequentially compact. Then a map T is bf -continuous, ff -continuous, bb -continuous and fb -continuous at u .

Proof. Since $T: X \rightarrow Y$ is b^* -continuous at u and (X, q) is forward sequentially compact by Proposition 3.21, a map T is bb -continuous and fb -continuous at u , and by Theorem 3.24, a map T is f^* -continuous then, by Proposition 3.23, a map T is ff -continuous and bf -continuous at u .

- Corollary 3.27. Assume $T: (X, C) \rightarrow (Y, q)$ is f^* -continuous at u , if (Y, q) is backward sequentially compact, then a map T is bf -continuous, ff -continuous, bb -continuous and fb -continuous at u .

- Lemma 3.28. Assume (X, C) is a CMS and $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ a sequence in X . Assume there is an order of non-negative natural numbers $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ such that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n < \infty$, in which $C(u_n, u_{n+1}) \leq \lambda_n M$, for some $M \in P$, and for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then, the sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is Cauchy order in (X, C) .

Proof. For $n > m$, we get,

$$C(u_m, u_n) \leq C(u_m, u_{m+1}) + C(u_{m+1}, u_{m+2}) + \cdots + C(u_{n-1}, u_n) \leq M \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \gamma_i$$

suppose $c \in \text{int } P$ and choose $\delta > 0$ such that $c + N_\delta(0) \subset P$ where,

$$N_\delta(0) = \{v \in E : \|v\| < \delta\}$$

since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \gamma_n < \infty$, there exists an actual number n_0 to the extent that for all $m \geq n_0$ $M \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \gamma_i \in N_\delta(0)$, also $-M \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \gamma_i \in N_\delta(0)$ since $c + N_\delta(0)$ is open. Thus, $c + N_\delta(0) \in \text{int } P$; that is $c - M \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \gamma_i \in \text{int } P$. Thus, $M \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \gamma_i \ll c$ for $m \geq n_0$ and so, $C(u_m, u_n) \ll c$ for $n > m \geq n_0$. Thus, $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a Cauchy order.

- Theorem 3.29. Assume (X, C) is a complete Hausdorff CMS, (X, q) a QCMS and suppose $T: (X, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is a b^* -continuous mapping. Suppose that there are functions $\eta, \lambda, \zeta, \mu, \xi: X \rightarrow [0, 1)$ which satisfy the following for $u, v \in X$,

- (1) $\eta(T(u)) \leq \eta(u), \lambda(T(u)) \leq \lambda(u), \zeta(T(u)) \leq \zeta(u), \mu(T(u)) \leq \mu(u)$ and $\xi(T(u)) \leq \xi(u)$
- (2) $\eta(u) + \lambda(u) + \zeta(u) + \mu(u) + \xi(u) < 1$
- (3) $q(T(u), T(v)) \leq \eta(u)q(u, v) + \lambda(u)q(u, T(u)) + \zeta(u)q(v, T(v)) + \mu(u)q(T(u), v) + \xi(u)q(v, T(v))$
- (4) $C(T(u), T(v)) \leq \eta(u)C(u, v) + \lambda(u)C(u, T(u)) + \zeta(u)C(v, T(v)) + \mu(u)C(T(u), v) + \xi(u)C(u, T(v))$

T then has a distinctive fixed point.

Proof. Let $u_0 \in X$ be arbitrary and fixed, and we consider the sequence of orbit of u_0 , $u_n = T(u_{n-1})$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If we take $u = u_{n-1}$ and $v = u_n$ in (4) we have,

$$\begin{aligned} C(u_n, u_{n+1}) &= C(T(u_{n-1}), T(u_n)) \\ &\leq \eta(u_{n-1})C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \lambda(u_{n-1})C(u_{n-1}, T(u_{n-1})) + \\ &\quad \zeta(u_{n-1})C(u_n, T(u_n)) + \mu(u_{n-1})C(T(u_{n-1}), u_n) + \xi(u_{n-1})C(u_{n-1}, T(u_n)) \\ &= \eta(T(u_{n-2}))C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \lambda(T(u_{n-2}))C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \\ &\quad \zeta(T(u_{n-2}))C(u_n, u_{n+1}) + \mu(T(u_{n-2}))C(T(u_{n-2}), u_n) + \\ &\quad \xi(T(u_{n-2}))C(u_{n-1}, u_{n+1}) \\ &\leq \eta(u_{n-2})C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \lambda(u_{n-2})C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \zeta(u_{n-2})C(u_n, u_{n+1}) + \\ &\quad \xi(u_{n-2})(C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + C(u_n, u_{n+1})) \\ &\quad \vdots \\ &\leq \eta(u_0)C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \lambda(u_0)C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \zeta(u_0)C(u_n, u_{n+1}) + \xi(u_0)(C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + C(u_n, u_{n+1})) \\ &= \eta(u_0)C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \lambda(u_0)C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \zeta(u_0)C(u_n, u_{n+1}) + \xi(u_0)C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \\ &\quad \xi(u_0)C(u_n, u_{n+1}) \\ &= (\eta(u_0) + \lambda(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + \zeta(u_0)C(u_n, u_{n+1}) + \xi(u_0)C(u_n, u_{n+1}) \\ &= (\eta(u_0) + \lambda(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_{n-1}, u_n) + (\zeta(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_n, u_{n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

so,

$$C(u_n, u_{n+1}) - (\zeta(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_n, u_{n+1}) \leq (\eta(u_0) + \lambda(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_{n-1}, u_n)$$

so,

$$C(u_n, u_{n+1})(1 - (\zeta(u_0) + \xi(u_0))) \leq (\eta(u_0) + \lambda(u_0) + \xi(u_0))C(u_{n-1}, u_n)$$

so,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C(u_n, u_{n+1}) &\leq \left(\frac{\eta(u_0) + \lambda(u_0) + \xi(u_0)}{1 - \zeta(u_0) - \xi(u_0)} \right) C(u_{n-1}, u_n) \\
 &= h C(u_{n-1}, u_n) \\
 &\leq h^2 C(u_{n-2}, u_{n-1}) \\
 &\vdots \\
 &\leq h^n C(u_0, u_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

thus, by Lemma 3.28, $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is Cauchy in X . Because of completeness of X and T is a b^* -continuous mapping, there exists $w \in X$ such that $u_n \rightarrow w$ and $u_{n+1} = T(u_n) \xrightarrow{b} T(w)$. For uniqueness, let w_1 be another fixed point of T , then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 q(w, w_1) &= q(T(w), T(w_1)) \\
 &\leq \eta(w)q(w, w_1) + \lambda(w)q(w, T(w)) + \zeta(w)q(w_1, T(w_1)) + \mu(w)q(T(w), w_1) + \xi(w)q(w, T(w_1)) \\
 &= \eta(w)q(w, w_1) + \lambda(w)q(w, w) + \zeta(w)q(w_1, w_1) + \mu(w)q(w, w_1) + \xi(w)q(w, w_1) \\
 &= \eta(w)q(w, w_1) + \mu(w)q(w, w_1) + \xi(w)q(w, w_1) \\
 &= (\eta(w) + \mu(w) + \xi(w))q(w, w_1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore; $\eta(w) + \mu(w) + \xi(w) \geq 1$, contradicts to (2). Thus, $q(w, w_1) = 0 \implies w = w_1$.

- Corollary 3.30. Assume (X, C) is a complete Hausdorff CMS, (X, q) a QCMS and suppose $T: (X, C) \rightarrow (X, q)$ is a b^* -continuous mapping. Suppose that there are functions $\eta, \lambda, \mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1)$, which gratify the following for $u, v \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\eta(T(u)) \leq \eta(u), \lambda(T(u)) \leq \lambda(u) \text{ and } \mu(T(u)) \leq \mu(u), \\
 (1) \quad &\eta(u) + 2\lambda(u) + 2\mu(u) < 1 \\
 (2) \quad &q(T(u), T(v)) \leq \eta(u)q(u, v) + \lambda(u)(q(u, T(v)) + q(v, T(v))) + \mu(u)(q(T(u), v) + q(u, T(v))) \\
 (3) \quad &C(T(u), T(v)) \leq \eta(u)C(u, v) + \lambda(u)(C(u, T(u)) + C(v, T(v))) + \mu(u)(C(T(u), v) + C(u, T(v)))
 \end{aligned}$$

then, T has a unique fixed point.

4. CONCLUSION

This study was mainly concerned with introducing four new notions of continuity of mapping, some theorems and propositions comparing these new notions to each other, illustrating them with some examples. Furthermore, in this paper, the fixed-point theorem of this newly introduced notion has been introduced. Future research can investigate a unique fixed point between CMS and QCMS to prove a fixed point between QCMS and CMS.

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